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Titania Nanoparticles as modified Photocatalyst

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Introduction: Since last many decades titania (TiO₂)-nanoparticle (NP) has been extensively studied owing to its prime characteristics as low cost, high stability, non-toxicity, biologically inertness, redox ability, and environmentally friendly merits (1, 2). The bandgap is the key factor to determine the photo-response ability for the TiO₂ NPs. Due to poor light absorption ability and low charge separation efficiency of pure anatase TiO₂, such limitations occur under normal conditions. Thus, an adaptation for the photo-response of anatase TiO₂ to match the solar spectrum is an important scientific challenge. Therefore, band-gap tuning is essential to make TiO₂ active under the broader band of the solar energy. Nowadays, the photo-response ability in the term of photocatalytic activity of TiO₂ can be controlled through synthesis of nano-composite materials which allows the improvement and tuning the characteristics (2). In this view of finding, the different synthetic approaches have created materials with different shape and size as effective morphological characteristics. Therefore, the synthetic trend can create and alter the mid-band-gap electronic states of the semiconductor material such as TiO₂ (2). For TiO₂ photocatalysis, the observed modification undergoes through recombination of photogenerated species, and it can alter the charge migration. These are essential aspects of TiO₂ photocatalyst for having a good photo-response ability and hence improved photocatalytic performance through easy UV-visible light absorption. In this direction, the doping approach has been proven to be a promising tool to form a TiO₂ nanocomposite by incorporating a different atom into the TiO₂ lattice. The dopant can trap the photogenerated charge carriers (electrons and holes) and promote the interfacial charge-transfer processes, which help to form quick recombination (2). This concept has been applied to introduce metallic species into the TiO₂ matrix to reduce the bandgap for solar light utilization in photocatalysis. We have synthesized Ag-doped titania (Ag/TiO₂) by varying different silver content using non-aqueous sol-gel synthesis route followed by calcination at different temperatures.

Methods: In sol-gel synthetic route, titanium tetra *iso*-propoxide (20 wt. %) was dropwise added to the dry methanol containing AgNO₃ (0.75, 1.5, 2.5, 3.5, 5.0 and 7.5 at %) with continuous stirring at room temperature. NH₃ solution was added to the above solution of the mixture to attain pH of 9-10 and obtained gel was further stirred for another 2 h at room temperature. The gel was filtered, washed with deionized water and methanol, and dried at room temperature for 2 h and then at 80 °C for 12 h. Finally, the dried gel was calcined at 400 °C for 4 h to obtain Ag/TiO₂. The obtained Ag/TiO₂ samples have been characterized by various instrumental methods of analysis and explored their photocatalytic activity by conducting a degradation study of methylene blue (MB) dye under UV-light irradiation using photocatalytic reactor.

Results & Discussions: The X-ray diffraction patterns of Ag/TiO₂ samples show the presence of an anatase phase and the transmission electron microscopy (TEM) images confirming the presence of Ag-NPs on the TiO₂ surface like a TiO₂-supported silver NP catalyst. The photoluminescence study revealed that Ag-NPs are effective in reducing the charge carrier recombination by capturing the electrons from TiO₂. Among the Ag/TiO₂ samples, 7.5 at % of Ag in Ag/TiO₂ was exhibited with high % of MB dye degradation indicating more photocatalytic active compared to other samples and pure anatase TiO₂.

Conclusions: The report reveals the role of dopant to enhance the photocatalytic activity of TiO₂ significantly when the dopant is doped chemically at suitable amounts. Also, suggests studying the photo-response ability of various metals (Ag, Au, Cu, etc.) doped semiconductors.

Keywords: Titania, Nanoparticle, Nanocomposite, Photocatalysis

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